

GANDALF: A LLM-based approach to map bark beetle outbreaks in semantic stories of Sentinel-2 images

Vincenzo Pasquadibisceglie
Dipartimento di Informatica,
Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo
Moro
Bari, via Orabona, 4, Italy
vincenzo.pasquadibisceglie@uniba.it

Vito Recchia
Dipartimento di Informatica,
Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo
Moro
Bari, via Orabona, 4, Italy
vito.recchia@uniba.it

Annalisa Appice
Dipartimento di Informatica,
Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo
Moro
Bari, via Orabona, 4, Italy
annalisa.appice@uniba.it

Donato Malerba
Dipartimento di Informatica,
Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo
Moro
Bari, via Orabona, 4, Italy
donato.malerba@uniba.it

Giuseppe Fiameni
NVIDIA AI Technology Center
Santa Clara, California, US
gfiameni@nvidia.com

Abstract

Huge spruce forest areas have been damaged by massive bark beetle outbreaks across Europe during the past few years. Hence, forest health management requires large-scale inventory of bark beetle outbreaks to plan actions for promptly mitigating forest tree dieback. Deep learning techniques have recently achieved amazing results in imagery semantic segmentation tasks by dominating the recent research for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images of forest areas. In addition, due to the impressive performance of Large Language Models (LLMs) in natural language understanding and generation tasks, LLMs have started attracting attention in multiple fields. In this paper, we describe GANDALF: an approach that leverages the potential of LLMs for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images of forest areas. Specifically, we take advantage of the rich context of textual data to transform Sentinel-2 images in smart data ready for boosting accurate semantic segmentation modeling. We use a foundation LLM model to account for the text encoding of the spectral-spatial imagery context information. We fine-tune the LLM model to perform the semantic segmentation of forest images and use the Integrated Gradients (IG) algorithm to explain how each spectral-spatial information has an effect on the bark beetle outbreak detection. We assess the effectiveness of the proposed approach in a case study regarding bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images of forest scenes in Czech Republic.

CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → **Natural language processing; Supervised learning by classification;** • **Applied computing** → **Environmental sciences.**

Keywords

Large Language Models, Fine-tuning, Semantic Segmentation, explainable AI, Sentinel-2 Images, Bark Beetle Outbreak Inventory

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1 Introduction

Forests and other wooded land cover close to half of the European land surface and coniferous forests are the most frequently occurring forests in Europe. Healthy forests play a crucial role supporting the ecological functions and mitigating consequences of pollution and climate changes. So preserving coniferous forest vitality is mandatory for the environmental and economic well-being of European ecosystems. However, there are several disturbance agents (e.g., insect outbreaks, wildfires, windrows) that make the European forest ecosystem vulnerable to destruction and unhealthy condition by causing an increase in forest tree mortality. As an example, since 2018, bark beetles and other biotic agents have ruined vast swathes of conifer forests in Europe and are expected to further intensify due to climate change.

Bark beetles are small, tree killer insects that reproduce beneath the bark of coniferous trees, depositing their eggs under the bark and swarming when the temperature is higher. Monitoring bark beetle outbreaks is certainly a crucial task to quantify and promptly mitigate the consequences of bark beetle infestations and enable forest managers to perform informed tree sanitation cuts. Nowadays, foresters mainly monitor bark beetle outbreaks during field surveys. While this method offers detailed insights, it can be costly, time-consuming, and challenging to scale. On the other hand, recent advancements in remote sensing technologies have made many free satellite images of forests available, improving forest health monitoring. Sentinel-2 satellites capture high-resolution images using thirteen spectral bands every five days. The Copernicus Open

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Access Hub provides free access to these images, promoting the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for forest health assessments [9]

Recent remote sensing studies [1, 19] have shown that bark beetle outbreaks affect biophysical and biochemical properties of trees, so the signs of the infestation are recorded in the Sentinel-2 images of the infested areas. This has prompted several recent studies to use AI to perform the inventory of bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images [15]. According to the recent boom of Deep Learning (DL) in multiple fields, the remote sensing literature has explored the performance of various DL models, including Multi-layer Deep Neural Network [2], Convolutional Neural Network [23, 25] or U-Net [4, 6, 24] models trained for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images. On the other hand, due to the recent focus on Large Language Models (LLMs), LLMs start attracting attention in multiple fields (e.g., [12, 18]) commonly using AI and DL methods.

This paper introduces a LLM scenario for Earth observation to capitalize on semantic information that is implicitly available within Sentinel-2 images. Specifically, we propose GANDALF: a large Language model-based approach for semantic segmentation of Sentinel-2 images of Forest areas, which converts Sentinel-2 images of forest scenes into semantic contextual stories and leverages a fine-tuning technique to transfer a foundation LLM model, Bert-medium [22], to the detection of bark beetle outbreaks. In addition, GANDALF uses the Integrated Gradients (IG) algorithm [21] to score the word tokens of the Sentinel-2 imagery semantic story and identify spectral data characteristics that disclose symptoms of bark beetle outbreaks. GANDALF was evaluated in a case study regarding bark beetle outbreaks localized in Czech Republic in September 2020. The evaluation study showed that fine-tuning a foundation LLM in the considered domain can outperform several state-of-the-art deep neural models commonly used for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images. In addition, the exploration of explanations obtained with the IG algorithm discloses information on which tokens of the semantic stories of Sentinel-2 images better reveal symptoms of bark beetle outbreaks.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces relevant related works. Section 3 describe the basics on Sentinel-2 imagery. Section 4 describes the proposed approach, while Section 5 reports the experimental evaluation and discusses the related findings. Finally, Section 6 concludes, drawing conclusions.

2 Related work

Several remote sensing studies have recently explored the use of AI techniques for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images. On the other hand, with the boom of LLMs, a few recent studies have started the exploration of the potential of LLMs in remote sensing. Based on these premises, this related work overview is organized into two main fronts. First we delve into recent remote sensing studies that incorporate AI and, in particular, DL techniques, for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images. On the other front, we describe the preliminary study to leverage LLMs in remote sensing applications.

2.1 Bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images

Recent research for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images have been conducted in the supervised setting by addressing

an imagery semantic segmentation task. Several seminal studies [5–7, 16] still use machine learning algorithms for recognizing bark beetle outbreaks through pixel-wise classification of Sentinel-2 data. Both [6] and [5] also integrate a post-hoc XAI technique to identify spectral bands that mainly guide global decisions of models.

On the other hand, DL strategies have recently seen a massive rise in popularity in several Earth observation applications and, consequently, also in bark beetle outbreak detection. For example, [6] and [24] evaluate the performance of deep semantic segmentation algorithms such as U-Net and FCN-8 as a contribution of their evaluation study. [2] performs an evaluation study including U-Net and DNN models for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images. This study augments spectral data with spectral-spatial data synthesized through pixel neighborhoods to account for spatial arrangement of data. [3] compares the performance of U-Net models trained by applying several data fusion techniques to process Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 images simultaneously. Both [23] and [25] analyze the performance of CNN models trained for mapping bark beetle outbreaks in several types of satellite images, included Sentinel-2 images. However, these study use deep neural models as black boxes without paying any attention to explain decisions of black-boxes.

2.2 LLMs in remote sensing

Although LLMs have recently attracted some attention in the remote sensing domain, the scientific literature on the implementation of LLMs for Earth observation remains relatively scan. Preliminary remote sensing investigations have explored LLMs mainly in image captioning and visual question answering [13]. These studies commonly consider multi-model approaches that use LLMs to process textual information (e.g., imagery captions) collected in addition to imagery data, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the scene. The potential of combining LLM capabilities and visual image analysis through Vision Language Models has been recently analyzed within Visual ChatGPT for generating textual descriptions of images, performing edge and straight line detection, and conducting image segmentation by using text-based guidance [17]. Recent studies have started the investigation of several text-supervised semantic segmentation methods that use text descriptions for guidance in image segmentation tasks that employs a text encoder to calculate embeddings of descriptive input labels in conjunction with a transformer-based image encoder [20]. These approaches are mainly used to mitigate the need for extensive manual labeling to fuel accurate supervision. However, vision language studies consider color images, neglecting multi-spectral images recorded with Sentinel-2 and considered in this paper. In addition, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that starts the exploration of how a foundation LLM can be adapted for mapping bark beetle outbreaks based on imagery information of forest areas.

3 Basics on Sentinel-2 imagery

Sentinel-2 is an Earth observation mission from the Copernicus Program that acquires optical imagery at high spatial resolution (10 m to 60 m) by covering the majority of the Earth's surface with a repeat cycle of 5 days. In particular, the Sentinel-2 satellite constellation retrieves multi-spectral radiometric data (13 bands) in the

Table 1: Sentinel-2 band description. Band mapping: B1: Coastal aerosol, B2: Blue, B3: Green, B4: Red, B5: Red edge 1, B6: Red edge 2, B7: Red edge 3, B8: Near Infrared Narrow (NIR), B8A: Narrow Near Infrared Narrow (NIR-A), B9: Water vapor, B10: SWIR Cirrus, B11: SWIR 1, B12: SWIR 2.

Band	Spatial Resolution (m)	Central Wavelength (nm)
B1	60	443
B2	10	490
B3	10	560
B4	10	665
B5	20	705
B6	20	740
B7	20	783
B8	10	842
B8A	20	865
B9	60	940
B10	60	1376.9
B11	20	1610
B12	20	2190

visible, near infrared, and short wave infrared parts of the spectrum through two satellites (Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B). Sentinel-2 spectral bands with spatial resolution, central Wavelength and band name are described in Table 3. The band B10 is commonly ignored, since it is reserved for atmospheric corrections. Sentinel-2 spectral bands with different spatial resolutions from 10 meters are re-sampled at the same pixel size of 10 meters resolution.

Let us consider an Earth scene S that is observed using a Sentinel-2 sensor. S is a grid of $n_S \times m_S$ pixels so that every pixel (i, j) of S is a region of 10 square meters of the Earth's surface. A Sentinel-2 image of scene S is a tensor X_S with size $n_S \times m_S \times d$, which represents a collection of spectral vectors measured on a d -dimensional selection of the Sentinel-2 spectrum over the scene grid of $n_S \times m_S$ pixels. The map of bark beetle outbreaks of a scene S is a binary mask Y_S with size $n_S \times m_S$ so that every frame $Y_S(i, j)$ is a binary value with two opposite semantic labels: "healthy" (0) and "damaged" (1), where "healthy" denotes the absence of a bark beetle infestation hotspot in the pixel, while "damaged" denotes the presence of a bark beetle infestation hotspot in the pixel. We assume, in this study, that X_S and Y_S are co-located in time and space.

A pixel neighborhood is a set of pixels surrounding a target pixel within a scene. In this study, we consider square-shaped pixel neighborhoods. So, given a user-defined, positive, integer parameter k to define the neighborhood size, the pixel neighborhood $N(i, j, S)$ is the pixel set that covers the $(2k + 1)^2$ pixels surrounding target pixel (i, j) in scene S , that is:

$$N(i, j, S) = \{(i', j') \in S \mid i - k \leq i' \leq i + k, \quad j - k \leq j' \leq j + k\}. \quad (1)$$

For each Sentinel-2 spectral band recorded pixel-wise in a Sentinel-2 spectral vector, the pixel-wise spectral-spatial context of the band can be obtained by measuring the minimum, maximum, average, median and standard deviation of the spectral band across the pixel neighborhood [2]. Specifically, let $1 \leq k \leq d$ be a Sentinel-2 spectral band, the spectral-spatial context of k at pixel (i, j) of X_S is

Figure 1: GANDALF pipeline.

obtained as:

$$\min(i, j, k) = \min_{(i', j') \in N(i, j, S)} X(i', j', k), \quad (2)$$

$$\max(i, j, k) = \max_{(i', j') \in N(i, j, S)} X(i', j', k), \quad (3)$$

$$\text{avg}(i, j, k) = \text{avg}_{(i', j') \in N(i, j, S)} X(i', j', k), \quad (4)$$

$$\text{median}(i, j, k) = \text{median}_{(i', j') \in N(i, j, S)} X(i', j', k), \quad (5)$$

$$\text{stdev}(i, j, k) = \text{stdev}_{(i', j') \in N(i, j, S)} X(i', j', k). \quad (6)$$

4 The GANDALF approach

In this section, we illustrate the learning stage of the remote sensing approach GANDALF. This takes a training set \mathcal{T} that is composed of a collection of Sentinel-2 images of forest scenes and the collection of the masks of the bark beetle outbreaks mapped in the considered scenes. It represents multispectral data acquired through Sentinel-2 as semantic stories of remotely sensed forest scenes and use fine-tuning to fit a LLM to these stories, in order to map bark beetle outbreaks. The overall picture of the learning stage of GANDALF approach is shown in Figure 1.

4.1 Extracting semantic stories

GANDALF extracts semantic stories from the imagery pixels recorded in the labeled Sentinel-2 tensors of \mathcal{T} . In particular, it transforms each imagery Sentinel-2 pixel into a semantic story according to a narrative skeleton. This skeleton defines a semantic context of the spectral vector recorded by Sentinel-2 in the given pixel and the spectral-spatial vector obtained aggregating the Sentinel-2 spectral vectors recorded in the pixel neighborhood. In GANDALF, we use the following narrative skeleton to generate the semantic story of a pixel:

⟨Band name⟩ is ⟨Pixel value⟩
ranging between minimum ⟨Minimum value⟩ and
maximum ⟨Maximum value⟩
with average ⟨Average value⟩
median ⟨Median value⟩ and
deviation ⟨Deviation value⟩.

The narrative skeleton includes non-terminal symbols ⟨·⟩ to denote the name of the Sentinel-2 spectral band, the value of the band measured in the pixel and the values of the band measured in the pixel neighborhood through the considered aggregate operators. Accordingly, the semantic story of an imagery pixel is the concatenation of the semantic sentences generated with the narrative skeleton reported above and adopted to describe each

Sentinel-2 band in the pixel: a semantic sentence is generated for each Sentinel-2 band. In particular, each sentence is obtained from the Sentinel-2 imagery band by replacing each non-terminal symbol of the narrative skeleton with the name of the band, the value of the corresponding band in the imagery pixel and the aggregates measured for the band in the pixel neighborhood, respectively.

4.2 LLM-based model

GANDALF uses a deep neural network to perform the semantic segmentation of a Sentinel-2 image (i.e., to assign each pixel of a Sentinel-2 image to a semantic label between “healthy” and “damaged”). This network encloses Bert-medium as the initial part of the model and a task-specific head as the final part of the model. Bert-medium [22] is a compact pre-trained variant of BERT. The choice of Bert-medium is based on results of the comparative study described in [22] that shows that Bert-medium can outperform several LLMs in several tasks (i.e., sentiment classification, natural language inference and textual entailment).¹ As reported in [22], Bert-medium includes 8 hidden layers (transformer blocks) and 8 self-attention heads with the hidden embedding size set equal to 512 and the filter size set equal to 2048 for a total of 41.7M parameters. Each transformer block is an encoder block with self-attention layers. In addition, the task-specific head used for the final decision is composed of a dense layer with size equal to 128 and a final layer for the binary classification with the Sigmoid activation function.

In GANDALF, the parameters of the foundation Bert-medium model are fine-tuned on the semantic stories of Sentinel-2 imagery data based on the gradient computed on the binary cross entropy loss function. However, based on [11], the fine-tuning of a foundation LLM model may higher accuracy in a decision task by performing a step of domain adaptation before training a task-specific head. Accordingly, we perform a step of domain adaptation to boost the performance of the semantic segmentation task by allowing the Bert-medium model to avoid considering the domain-specific words of the remote sensing corpus as rare tokens. We perform the domain adaptation stage of Bert-medium along the Masked Language Model (MLM) task described in [8]. This is done by randomly masking some tokens of each semantic story in the training set and adapting the parameters of the foundation Bert-medium to predict the masked tokens. The Bert-medium model with parameters adapted through the domain adaptation step is finally fine-tuned with the task-specific head on the downstream decision task for bark beetle outbreak detection.

4.3 IG-based explanation

The Integrated Gradients (IG) technique [21] is a local, XAI technique that uses gradients to explain the effect of input dimensions on DL model decisions. In GANDALF, the IG technique is used to compute the gradient value for each input token of the semantic story of a Sentinel-2 pixel assigned to a semantic label. Given a semantic story of a Sentinel-2 pixel, first IG initializes a vector of zeros with one zero for each text token in the semantic story of a pixel. Then, for each token of the pixel semantic story, it computes the gradient of the decision. This gradient value measures the effect of a change of the considered token on the model decision.

¹However, any other foundation LLM can be evaluated for the scope of this paper.

The gradient values are integrated along the network layers from the initial vector to the actual input by resorting to approximation techniques (e.g., Riemann sum or Gauss-Legendre quadrature rule). The higher the integrated gradient value measured for an input token, the more the prediction of the model is affected by possible changes in the considered token.

5 Evaluation

This experimental study aims at exploring the accuracy performance of the LLM-based remote sensing approach described here in a study dataset regarding cases of bark beetle outbreaks appeared in September 2020 in Czech Republic. In addition, we analyze decision explanations recovered with the IG technique at both global and local level, to understand what spectral-spatial tokens of a pixel semantic story mainly contribute to the accuracy of the inventory performed in the study.

5.1 Case study data and experimental set-up

We considered a case study that involves 200 non-overlapping forest scenes spanned across the Czech Republic. The considered scenes hosted bark beetle outbreaks that were likely caused by the hot summer droughts in 2020. The ground truth map of these outbreaks was acquired in September 2020 and recorded in DEFID2 database [10]. We used the ESA Copernicus open access hub with the Google Earth Engine APIs to download cloud-free Sentinel-2 images of the considered scenes. For each scene, we selected the Sentinel-2 images acquired in September 2020 which achieved the minimum cloudiness index. This index was computed as the percentage of imagery pixels that the SCL algorithm [14] recognizes as noise, defective, dark, cloud, cloud shadow or thin cirrus. If several images achieve the minimum value of the cloudiness index in September 2020, then we selected the most recent Sentinel-2 image of this selection. The images were downloaded in the 3857 EPSG system. In the obtained Sentinel-2 dataset, the size of images varies from 33×36 to 260×238 pixels at 10 square meters resolution, while the percentage of infested territory per scene varies from 4.14% to 54.81% of the scene surface. The total percentage of damaged territory of the entire scene collection is 14.59%. The semantic segmentation model development and its evaluation were conducted by considering 160 random scenes (covering 1014708 pixels at 10 square meters resolution) as training scene set and 40 left-out scenes (covering 198253 pixels) as testing scene set. Figure 2 shows the map of the location of study scenes in the Czech Republic, as well as the partitioning of the scene set in the training scene set and testing scene set.

5.2 Implementation details

GANDALF was implemented in Python 3.9.18-64 bit version, using Torch 2.1.1 as the back-end. The source code of the proposed approach is available on the GitHub repository². The pre-trained version of Bert-medium used in the evaluation study is available on Hugging Face repository³. For the fine-tuning process, we adopted the AdamW optimizer with learning rate equal to $1e-5$ and batch

²<https://github.com/vinspdb/GANDALF>

³<https://huggingface.co/prajjwal1/bert-medium>

Figure 2: Location of the centroids of the study scenes in the Czech Republic. The red circles are the training set scenes, while the blue circles are the testing set scenes.

size equal to 1024. The training stage was performed using Accelerate⁴. The 50% of semantic stories collected in a training set were used for the domain adaptation stage, while the remaining 50% of semantic stories were used for the fine-tuning in the downstream task. The percentage of tokens masked during the domain adaptation step was set equal to 15% of tokens. Finally, the code of GANDALF integrated the LayerIntegratedGradients version of IG that is available in Captum library.⁵

5.3 Results and discussion

In this Section, we illustrate the results achieved in:

- the accuracy performance study conducted to explore the effect of both the spectral-spatial information and the domain adaptation step on the accuracy of the semantic segmentation performed with GANDALF (Section 5.3.1);
- the comparative study conducted to analyze the accuracy performance of GANDALF and some related DL methods commonly used for semantic segmentation and bark beetle outbreak detection studies (Section 5.3.1);
- the qualitative analysis of the explanation insights produced with the IG technique in GANDALF (Section 5.3.3).

In both the performance study and the comparative study, we evaluated the accuracy performance by measuring the F1-score (F1) and Intersection-over-Union (IoU) metrics. Both metrics are commonly measured in semantic segmentation problems. The F1 score measures the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, that is, $F1 = \frac{2 \text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$. In particular, the Precision = $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$ is the fraction of pixels correctly classified in the class “positive” (TP) among pixels of the considered class (TP + FP). The Recall = $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$ is the fraction of pixels correctly classified in a specific class “positive” (TP) among pixels classified in the considered class (TP + FN). We computed the F1 score per each class, i.e., F1(D) was computed considering the class “damaged” as the class “positive” and the class “healthy” as the class “negative”, while F1(H) was computed considering the class “healthy” as the class “positive” and the class “damaged” as the class “negative”. As a summary metric, we also computed the MacroF1 that is the average of each F1 score computed per class, i.e., $\text{macroF1} = \frac{F1(H)+F1(D)}{2}$. Finally, the IoU score

⁴<https://pypi.org/project/accelerate/>

⁵<https://captum.ai/api/layer.html>

Table 2: Accuracy performance analysis: GANDALF with neighborhood radius k varying among 0 (no spectra-spatial feature generated), 1, 2 (default) and 3. The best results are in bold, while the runner-up results are underlined.

Model	F1 (D)	F1 (H)	Macro F1	IoU
GANDALF, $k = 0$	0.6246	0.9312	0.7779	0.4541
GANDALF, $k = 1$	0.6487	0.9335	0.7911	0.4801
GANDALF, $k = 2$ (*)	0.6863	<u>0.9361</u>	0.8112	0.5224
GANDALF, $k = 3$	<u>0.6804</u>	0.9375	<u>0.8089</u>	<u>0.5156</u>

is the ratio of the intersected area to the combined area of prediction and ground truth, that is, $\text{IoU} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP+FN}$, where the class “damaged” is considered as the class “positive” and the class “healthy” is considered as the class “negative”. The metrics are reported in percentages and computed on the Sentinel-2 images collected for the testing scenes of the case study. For each metric, the higher the value, the better the performance of the semantic segmentation maps predicted.

5.3.1 Accuracy performance study. Table 2 reports the results of the sensitivity study performed to explore the accuracy performance of GANDALF along the size k of the pixel neighborhood used to synthesize spectral-spatial information to feed pixel semantic stories. This analysis was performed by varying k among 0, 1, 2 and 3. Notably, the configuration of GANDALF with $k = 0$ corresponds to the baseline configuration, with no spectra-spatial information synthesized and only the pixel-wise spectral band values used to feed the semantic story of a pixel. The results show that accounting for spectral-spatial information boosts the performance of the GANDALF model. In fact, all configurations run with $k \geq 1$ outperform the configuration with $k = 0$. On the other hand, there is a remarkable gain in the ability of recognizing damages caused by bark beetle outbreaks achieved passing from $k = 1$ to $k = 2$, while this detection ability slightly decreases passing from $k = 2$ to $k = 3$. Based upon these results, we consider the configuration of GANDALF with $k = 2$ in the follow-up of this study. We note that, in this configuration, the spectral-spatial information used for producing a pixel semantic story was synthesized within a squared neighborhood surrounding the pixel and covering an area of 50 square meters. This is coherent with habits of bark beetles that commonly swarm across an area of several tens of meters during an outbreak event.

Table 3 reports the results of the ablation study done to explore the effectiveness of performing the MLM step of domain adaptation as a strategy to gain accuracy with the foundation LLM model fine-tuned in GANDALF. The results show that the semantic segmentation performed with the LLM model fine-tuned by performing the MLM-based domain adaptation outperforms the semantic segmentation model of the LLM fine-tuned without the MLM step of domain adaptation.

5.3.2 Comparative study. We compare the accuracy performance of GANDALF to that of DL methods commonly used in literature studies for bark beetle outbreak detection in Sentinel-2 images. In particular, as related methods we consider:

Table 3: Ablation analysis: accuracy performance of the LLM model fine-tuned without the MLM-based domain adaptation step versus the LLM model of GANDALF fine-tuned with the MLM step. The best results are in bold.

Model	F1 (D)	F1 (H)	Macro F1	IoU
GANDALF - no MLM	0.6616	0.9335	0.7975	0.4943
GANDALF	0.6863	0.9361	0.8112	0.5224

- MLP: a Multi-Layer Perceptron trained as a pixel-wise classification model from the vector representation of both the spectral band values and the spectral-spatial aggregation of band values. The MLP architecture was composed of a number of fully connected layers, varying between 3 and 6. The number of layers was selected by maximizing the F1 score computed on the class “damaged” for a validation set (20% of the training set) with the tree-structured Parzen estimator algorithm. The number of neurons per layer was a power of two, with the final layer having 32 neurons, and the output probabilities were obtained using the softmax activation function. The ReLU activation function was used in all the other hidden layers.
- UNET: a U-Net based architecture trained for the imagery semantic segmentation downstream task. It included an encoder repeating blocks with a 3×3 convolutional layer with a spatial dropout, a Batch Normalization layer and a 2×2 Max Pooling operation layer. At each down-sampling step of the encoder, the number of feature channels was increased. In the decoder, the feature map was up-sampled through a sequence of up-convolutions that halved the number of feature channels and concatenated the result with the features from the corresponding encoder layer. The classification of each pixel map was obtained by using the Sigmoid activation function. The ReLU was used in all hidden convolution layers. The Tversky loss was used.
- CNN: a Convolutional Neural Network trained for image classification. It handled each imagery pixel as a distinct image that represents the pixel within its pixel square neighborhood. The CNN architecture was defined with a variable number of Convolutional layers, which was automatically set with the tree-structured Parzen estimator algorithm during the training stage, and two Fully-Connected layers. A Dropout layer was placed between each pair of Convolutional layers to perform data regularization and prevent training data overfitting. In all layers, except the final classification layer, the Rectified Linear Unit function (ReLU) was used as the activation function. The Softmax activation function was used in the classification layer.

All methods used the tree-structured Parzen estimator algorithm for the hyper-parameter optimization. They were trained with the gradient-based optimization using the Adam update rule with the maximum number of epochs set equal to 150, and using an early-stopping approach to retain the best model (according to F1(D) metric). Notably, all the compared DL methods account for the spectral-spatial information. In fact, GANDALF and MLP consider

Table 4: Comparative accuracy analysis: GANDALF, MLP, UNET and CNN. The best results are in bold.

Model	F1 (D)	F1 (H)	Macro F1	IoU
GANDALF	0.6863	<u>0.9361</u>	0.8112	0.5224
MLP	<u>0.6849</u>	0.9272	0.8061	<u>0.5208</u>
UNET	0.6758	0.9078	0.7918	0.5103
CNN	0.6776	0.9370	<u>0.8073</u>	0.5124

Figure 3: Ground truth (GT) label mask and semantic segmentation masks predicted with GANDALF and the related methods: MLP, UNET and CNN, for one of the testing scenes of Czech Republic case study

spectral-spatial features synthesized over a pixel neighborhood, U-Net and CNN map relationships of spatial information between spectral pixels in convolution layers.

Table 4 reports the accuracy performance of the compared methods in the considered case study. The results show that GANDALF outperforms the related methods of this comparative study along F1(D), MacroF1 and IoU, being the runner-up along F1(H). In particular, the analysis of F1(D) and IoU shows that GANDALF can better separate the forest area damaged by the bark beetle outbreak from the healthy background, having MLP as runner-up. As GANDALF and MLP leverage spectral-spatial features, while UNET and CNN leverage convolution layers, these results also show that the step of spectral-spatial data engineering is an effective alternative to the use of convolution layers to account for spectral-spatial correlation appearing in Sentinel-2 imagery. Finally, Figure 3 shows an example of semantic segmentation maps predicted for one of the testing scenes of the considered case study by using GANDALF and the related methods: MLP, UNET and CNN.

5.3.3 Explanation study. In GANDALF, the IG technique was used to assign a numerical score to each token of a pixel semantic story for which a semantic label was decided with the Bert-medium model. The magnitude of the IG score describes the strength of the contribution of the token on the decision. Positive IG scores identify tokens that contribute positively to the classification, while negative IG scores identify tokens that contribute negatively. For example, Figure 4 shows the semantic story of a “damaged” pixel of a testing scene of the Czech Republic case study, where the IG scores computed for the separate tokens of the story have been highlighted according to their magnitude. Positive scores are in green, neutral scores are in white and negative scores are in red. The plot shows that the Bert-medium model of GANDALF sees the spectral and spectral-spatial values of the B2 (Blue) band, the

Band	Semantic story
B1	coastal aerosol is 370 ranging between minimum 346 and maximum 440 with average 375 , median 370 and deviation 31 .
B2	blue is 541 ranging between minimum 499 and maximum 618 with average 544 , median 549 and deviation 23 .
B3	green is 736 ranging between minimum 653 and maximum 775 with average 716 , median 715 and deviation 32 .
B4	red is 1004 ranging between minimum 930 and maximum 1116 with average 1005 , median 998 and deviation 63 .
B5	red - edge - 1 is 1414 ranging between minimum 1140 and maximum 1414 with average 1308 , median 1284 and deviation 98 .
B6	red - edge - 2 is 1878 ranging between minimum 1571 and maximum 2156 with average 1827 , median 1878 and deviation 178 .
B7	red - edge - 3 is 2234 ranging between minimum 1854 and maximum 2588 with average 2170 , median 2234 and deviation 219 .
B8	nir is 2630 ranging between minimum 2114 and maximum 2640 with average 2434 , median 2486 and deviation 159 .
B8A	narrow nir is 2669 ranging between minimum 2307 and maximum 2920 with average 2589 , median 2669 and deviation 197 .
B10	water vapor is 2678 ranging between minimum 2280 and maximum 2678 with average 2563 , median 2554 and deviation 141 .
B11	swir - 1 is 3186 ranging between minimum 2649 and maximum 3186 with average 2937 , median 2877 and deviation 213 .
B12	swir - 2 is 2091 ranging between minimum 1624 and maximum 2091 with average 1907 , median 1890 and deviation 153 .

Legend: ■ Negative □ Neutral ■ Positive

Figure 4: IG explanation produced for the semantic story of a “damaged” pixel of a testing scene of the Czech Republic case study

Figure 5: Average IG scores per token group (axis X) and spectral band (axis Y): “healthy” vs “damaged”

spectral value of B5 (Red edge 1) and the minimum value of B12 (SWIR 2) as the most positively relevant for the decision.

We grouped single tokens of each band-based sentence of the semantic story of a pixel in “token groups” defined as follows:

- Group “Value”: <Band name> is <Pixel value>
- Group “Min-Max”: <Band name> is ranging between minimum <Minimum value> and maximum <Maximum value>
- Group “Average”: <Band name> is with average <Average value>
- Group “Median”: <Band name> is with median <Median value>
- Group “Deviation”: <Band name> is with deviation <Deviation value>.

Hence, for each band-based sentence of a semantic story of a pixel, for each one of the token groups listed above, we computed the average of the IG scores associated with the tokens of

the considered group in the selected sentence. Figure 5 shows the maps of the average IG score computed per spectral band (axis Y) and token group (axis X) for pixels of classes “healthy” and “damaged”, respectively. Specifically, the IG scores were computed for the semantic stories of pixels of testing scenes and averaged on the classes: “healthy” and “damaged”, separately. In this way, the two maps provide a global explanation of the decision process showing which band-based token groups the Bert-medium model of GANDALF sees as the most positively relevant for the decisions regarding the two classes. In particular, the IG results of the considered case study show that the group of tokens (Value) to describe the spectral values of B4 (Red) and B2 (Blue) contain the most relevant information for decisions regarding “healthy” patches, while the ones to describe the spectral values of B4 (Red) and B5 (Red edge 1) contain the most relevant information for decisions regarding “damaged” patches. Notably, only some of the groups of tokens used to describe spectral-spatial values of bands B7 (Red edge 3), B8 (NIR), B8A (NIR-A) and B9 (Water vapor) – specifically, Min-Max, Average, Median and Standard Deviation for B7, Min-Max for B8 and B8A, and Min-Max and Average for B9 – have a positive effect on decisions of “healthy” patches. On the other hand, the majority of the tokens that describe the spectral and spectral-spatial information of the “damaged” pixels have a positive effect on decisions regarding these pixels. Finally, the B1 (Coastal aerosol) and B11 (SWIR 1) have a negative effect on decisions of both classes. In general, these explanation insights of the decision process of GANDALF highlight that the number of tokens having a positive effect on decisions regarding the “damaged” class is significantly greater than the number of tokens having a positive effect on decisions regarding the “healthy” class. This shows that the decision process concerning the forest damage caused by the bark beetle outbreak is, in general, more complex (in terms of information that drives the decision of the LLM model) than the decision process to delineate the healthy patches. Finally, we note that the B5 information enclosed in all groups of tokens considered in this study is among the most positive relevant for the decisions of the Bert-medium model of GANDALF on pixels in the class “damaged”. This supports one of the major conclusions drawn in

the seminal study of [1] that the Red-Edge information as one the most sensitive Sentinel-2 band to insect attack.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a LLM-based method to perform the inventory of forest tree dieback caused bark beetle outbreaks in Sentinel-2 images of forest scenes. The accuracy of the proposed method GANDALF was evaluated in a case study that regards forest scenes infested by bark beetle outbreaks mapped in September 2020 in Republic Czech. The obtained results preliminary show the effectiveness of both the semantic representation adopted to encode the Sentinel-2 data as semantic stories and the domain adaptation process used to fine-tune a foundation LLM model in the considered remote sensing task. The experimental study shows that the LLM model of GANDALF outperforms related models trained with DL methods commonly considered in the literature studies addressing the same task. Finally, the explanation evaluation discloses useful information on the effect of spectral information observed with Sentinel-2 satellite on the decision process of the adopted LLM model.

Beyond the valuable results achieved by showing that a foundation LLM model can be actually adapted to be effective in a remote sensing domain, this work paves the way for further investigations in the same field. With this regard, we intend to investigate how the proposed LLM-based approach can be extended to consider a semantic story of temporal patterns in addition to a semantic story of spectral-spatial patterns. Furthermore, we intend to extend the experimentation to new geographical areas and compare the performance of different LLMs in the same task. In addition, we intend to explore a multi-modal AI approach that performs fusion of imagery and text data to improve the accuracy of the decision model. Finally, we would explore how the proposed LLM-based approach may effectively be used to map tree dieback areas of Sentinel-2 images caused by different families of insects.

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